

Bailadeiras of Goa

By EDUARDO NOGUEIRA, Colégio Pedro II

Entry tags: Hinduism, Shaivism, Religious Group

"Bailadeiras" was the name used by Portuguese in Goa to refer to the groups of women who served the Hindu temples. Under this denomination were: the sacred dancers, known as Devadasi, Kalavant or Naiquine (in Sanskrit and Konkani); the Bhavins, responsible for the ritual cleaning of the temple; the Rajadasi, women also associated to the dance rituals of the temple; the Chedvans, women who served a lord and lived in the lands of the temple;

Date Range: 1510 CE - 1650 CE

Region: Goa

Region tags: India, Konkani, Goa

Goa before Portuguese conquer belonged to the Bijapur Sultanate, serving as a trade port connected to the Arabian and Persian market. After 1510 the island of Tisvadi, where the city is located, began to be modeled as the Portuguese politics demanded. Its architecture and space shapping were elaborated to create an "Asian Lisbon", what could be also seen in its political powers. Governed by a Viceroy, containing important and powerful Portuguese institutions and made to be a Catholic fortress, Goa was an important place of the Modern Europeans affairs in Orient.

Status of Participants:

✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: PEREZ, Rosa Maria. "O Tulsi e a Cruz": Antropologia e Colonialismo em Goa. Lisbon: Temas e Debates, 2012.
- Source 2: ALMEIDA, Suely Creusa Carneiro. "O sexo devoto: normatização e resistência feminina no Império Português - XVI - XVIII. Recife: UFPE, 2005.
- Source 3: CHAKRABORTHY, Kakolee. "Women as Devadasis. Origin and Growth of the Devadasi Profession. New Dheli: Deep & Deep Publications, 2000.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://archive.org/details/glossriolusoas00dalguoft>
- Source 1 Description: DALGADO, Sebastião Rodolpho. "Glossário Luso-Asiático". Lisbon: Academia de Ciências, 1855-1922, p.80-81. Entry about the Bailadeiras.
- Source 2 URL: <https://archive.org/details/in.ernet.dli.2015.292578/page/n65/mode/2up>

- Source 2 Description: MENDES, A. Lopes. "A India Portuguesa". Vol. 2. Lisbon: Imprensa Nacional, 1886, p.32-34. Topic about the Bavinas and Calavontes of Goa.
- Source 3 URL: <https://bibliografia.bnportugal.gov.pt/bnp/bnp.exe/registo?1828306>
- Source 3 Description: PEREZ, Rosa Maria. "O Tulsi e a Cruz": Antropologia e Colonialismo em Goa. Lisbon: Temas e Debates, 2012, p.103-133. Important book about aspects of Hindu-Portuguese cultural encounters and disputes since the 16th Century in Goa. The chapter 3 offers important social, political an cultural analysis about Goan bavinas and devadasis.

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <https://digitarq.arquivos.pt/details?id=2312781>
- Source 1 Description: Inquisitorial sentence of André Fernandez - 1563. The culprit was accused to have relations with a "gentia bailadora" (a Hindu Devadasi) and to have apostated, turning into Muslim.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: The Hindu temple women servers and artists, known generically by Portuguesees as "Bailadeiras", were persecuted over the 16th, 17th and 18th centuries by Portuguese Catholic authorities. This persecution was part of a bigger Portuguese Christian conversion project of its domains, applied strongly in Goa, capital of the Asian Portuguese Empire.

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– No

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– Yes

Notes: Daughters of bailadeiras used to be trained since their early years to also become bailadeiras. Therefore, the girls used to inherited the status and profession of their mothers.

Reference: Camila dos Anjos Domingos. *A Cruz e o Império: a expansão portuguesa e a cristianização das bailadeiras e viúvas em Goa (1567-1606)*. Seropédica: UFRRJ.

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– Yes

Notes: Girls assigned to be ballet dancers were ritually initiated into the arts and crafts of the profession from their first menstruation.

↳ Assigned by gender:

– Yes

Notes: Only women could become bailadeiras.

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Notes: The ritual known in Konkani as Xen was the initiation rite of the bailadeiras. In this moment, the girl who would become a bailadeira used to be married with the statue of a god of the temple where she would serve. Flowers or other girl dressed as a man were also used as "husbands" of the future bailadeira in this ritual.

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: As the bailadeiras used to be consorts of the brahmins of the temples where they served, this relationship was politically beneficial for that women. As important servers of Hindu temples, this powerful institution in India politics also supported those women. On the other hand, many temples were supported by pious Hindu kings, what contributed to the prosperity of the servers of the temples (as the bailadeiras) under this condition.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– Yes

Notes: The bailadeiras were sacred wives of the gods who lived in the temple where they served. If one of them married a man, the bailadeira would lose her status, becoming an outcaste person.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Field doesn't know

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: Although almost all the Hindu temples of Goa were destructed by Portuguese forces in the 16th century, the bailadeiras remained active in the "migrant" temples. Due the persecution, idols, part of the structure and servers (as the bailadeiras) migrated from the island of Goa to the lands out of Catholic jurisdiction. Built again, the monumental Hindu temples endured. There the bailadeiras continued their art.

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Field doesn't know

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– At home

– Only religious public space

– Some public spaces

Notes: It is known that there are remnants statues of bailadeiras/ devadasis in temples near Goa, as the Chennakeshava Temple of Belur, dating from the 12th century. Due this evidence, it is possible that there were, in ancient Hindu Goan temples, images of the bailadeiras. There are also statues of bailadeiras dating back to the 17th and 18th centuries, maybe used as decorations objects in other public or private spaces.

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– No

↳ Humans:
– Yes

↳ Other features of iconography:
– Yes

Notes: The iconography related to the bailadeiras present them in specific dance movements. Represented as dressed for rituals, their arms, hands, legs and feet are painted or sculpted in positions associated with their dance canons.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– I don't know

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: As hindu women, the bailadeiras followed the general and specific beliefs of their group (devadasis) and the temple where they served.

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– I don't know

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– I don't know

Are grave goods present:

– I don't know

Are formal burials present:

– I don't know

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– No

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: As followers of Shaiva, Vaishnava and Shakta traditions, the bailadeiras were consonant to the aspects of those cults.

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– I don't know

- ↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can reward:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can punish:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
 - Yes
- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
 - I don't know
- ↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - I don't know
 - ↳ In dreams:
 - Yes

- ↳ In trance possession:
 - Yes
- ↳ Through divination practices:
 - Yes
- ↳ Only through religious specialists:
 - No
- ↳ Only through monarch
 - No
- ↳ Other form of communication with living:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Previously human spirits are present:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:
 - Yes
 - ↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:
 - Yes
 - ↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:
 - I don't know
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - I don't know
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - I don't know

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - I don't know
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - I don't know
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - I don't know
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):
 - I don't know
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - I don't know
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings can reward:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– I don't know

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– No

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– I don't know

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– I don't know

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– I don't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– I don't know

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– I don't know

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:
– Strongly present and highlighted

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:
– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:
– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:
– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):
– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic

being:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:

– No

↳ Moral norms apply to:

– All individuals within society

Notes: The moral norms related to the bailadeiras, though they respected the general rules present in Hindu traditions, were more flexible about sexual norms. Differently from the other women, the bailadeiras had a considerable sexual freedom, thoughh they could not get married with regular men, as they were already married with the god of the temple where they served.

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: The Bailadeiras were not sexually constrained, having considerable sexual freedom. Associated to the lascive aspects of the gods and fertility, the dance and musical aspects of the Hindu rituals, exercised by the bailadeiras, embodied that features of Hindu cults.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Though this topic is here answered as "Field doesn't know", as Hindu women, it is possible that the Bailadeiras respected some food taboos, as this is a common feature in Hindu traditions.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– Yes

Notes: Understanding the "sacrifice" as a process of taking out anything of common use, the bailadeiras can be understand as sacrificed adult people. After all, they were dedicated to the temple life, getting married to a god that inhabited this place. Besides it, they were also forbidden to get married with "common men" and to live outside the temple, aspects that reinforce the idea of sacrificed women.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– Yes

Notes: Understanding the "sacrifice" as a process of taking out anything of common use, the sons and daughters of bailadeiras also used to be dedicated to the temple. The girls use to become Bailadeiras, inheriting the profession of their mothers. The boys used to become or dancers or musicians of the temple.

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: The bailadeiras were responsible of many important rituals of the temple routine. Because of that, they spent a big part of their time working in their religious duties.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Notes: The ethical precepts of the Bailadeiras referred to those present in the cults that they were part of and those related to their duties as devadasis.

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– Yes

Notes: The bailadeiras, though their relatively high ritual importance, were socially discriminated inside Hindu social structures. This fact, associated to the prejudicial Portuguese (and Christian, in general) perspective about them contributed to their marginalization.

Reference: Rosa Perez. *O Tulsi e a Cruz. Antropologia e colonialismo em Goa.* Lisboa: Círculo de Leitores. isbn: 978-989-644-187-6.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– I don't know

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– I don't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Yes

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– I don't know

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

Notes: The bailadeiras were known as wives of the gods to whom they were dedicated to. These gods, therefore, were their husbands.

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Bailadeiras belonged to a specific system, the Devadasi system, in which they were associated to a temple through marriage with a god. Even if they were under some level of authority of Brahmins responsible of the temple, they were in charge of important and indispensable rites, giving them power in the templary dynamics.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Hindu kings used to donate great sums of wealth to the temples in order to show piety to the gods and power to their subjects. Therefore, the bailadeiras also enjoyed the these resources given to the temple.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: The bailadeiras orally did transmitted their knowledge to their daughters, who would become later the next generation of bailadeiras of the temple. The temple, as educational insitutions, also provided some level of formal education to the girls that would become future bailadeiras.

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– No

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– I don't know

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– I don't know

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Under Portuguese rule, the Catholic Church, specially from the decade of 1530 and on, started an intense persecution against Hindu temples. Because of it, Bailadeiras and other Hindu servants and priests became under the vigilance of Christian clergymen.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Under Portuguese domain, all inhabitants of the island of Goa were under the jurisdiction of Portuguese forces. Although in the 16th century the "Foral de Usos e Costumes" elaborated by the "Vedor da Fazenda" Afonso Mexia did stipulated the rights of the different Hindu Goan groups, from 1530 and on, the situation of non Christian people in Goa changed. Under persecution of the Catholic Church associated to the Portuguese Crown, many Hindu groups escaped from Portuguese domains. In the case of the Bailadeiras, as they were interpreted by Europeans as pagan prostitutes associated to the Hindu temples and its gods, the religious judicial system of the Estado da Índia determined their expel from Portuguese lands.

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– I don't know

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

Notes: As many other members of Goan Hindu temples, Bailadeiras were forced to exile by Portuguese authorities from the decade of 1530.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– I don't know

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

Notes: As many other members of Goan Hindu temples, Bailadeiras were forced to ostracism by Portuguese authorities from the decade of 1530.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Notes: After the destruction of Goan Hindu temples by Portuguese authorities, many of the wealth that belonged to it became property of the Catholic Church in Goa. Therefore, great part of the goods of Bailadeiras, Brahmins associated to the priesthood in the temples and servants were seized by Portuguese forces in this process.

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– I don't know

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Under Portuguese rule and jurisdiction, Bailadeiras and other Hindu groups became part of the Estado da Índia, responding to its legal codes.

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Bailadeiras, as other Goan Hindu groups under the authority of Estado da Índia, were subject to the military Portuguese forces.

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Under Portuguese rule, the Portuguese language was gradually imposed to all Hindu groups that accepted or were forced to be converted to the Catholicism.

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Under Portuguese rule, the Portuguese written language was gradually imposed to all Hindu groups that accepted or were forced to be converted to the Catholicism.

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– I don't know

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: As a Hindu group, the Bailadeiras followed the Hindu calendar.

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Notes: Bailadeiras depended on the resources of the temple where they worked and lived. Because of it, food and other resources for their living belonged to the temple structure. The temple itself had its own lands dedicated to the production of its own food and other goods that would be dedicated to the cult or used and consumed by its servants, priests and priestesses.

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Jorge Silva Lúzio. *As bailadeiras. Devadasis dança e colonialidade na Índia Portuguesa - século XVIII.* São Paulo: PUC-SP.

Reference: Romila Thapar. *A History of India.* London: Penguin. isbn: 978-0-14-013835-1.

Reference: MATOS Luís de. *Imagens do Oriente no século XVI. Reprodução do Códice Português da Biblioteca Casanatense.* Lisboa: Imprensa Nacional - Casa da Moeda. isbn: 6405/84.

Reference: XAVIER Ângela Barreto. *A invenção de Goa. Poder imperial e conversões culturais nos séculos XVI e XVII.* Lisbon: Imprensa de Ciências Sociais. isbn: 978-972-671-209-1.

Reference: SUBRAHMANYAM Sanjay undefined. *O Império Asiático Português, 1500-1700. Uma história política e econômica.* Carnaxide: Difel. isbn: 972-29-0328-4.

Reference: BOXER Charles Ralph. *O império marítimo português. 1415 - 1825.* São Paulo: Companhia das Letras. isbn: 85-359-0292-9.

Entry/Answer References

Reference: Camila dos Anjos Domingos. *A Cruz e o Império: a expansão portuguesa e a cristianização das bailadeiras e viúvas em Goa (1567-1606).* Seropédica: UFRRJ.

Reference: Rosa Perez. *O Tulsi e a Cruz. Antropologia e colonialismo em Goa.* Lisboa: Círculo de Leitores. isbn: 978-989-644-187-6.